

**TITLE: THE ROLE OF ASTRAL EU H2020 PROJECT IN MAINSTREAMING WOMEN IN
AQUACULTURE IN NIGERIA**

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ABSTRACT

Nigeria with an annual potential of 2.5 million tonnes of fish from aquaculture produced only 316,727 tonnes in 2015 out of the domestic production of 1.027 million tonnes and total fish demand of 3.25 million tonnes. The government has put in place a lot of initiatives to increase aquaculture production which included the growth enhancement scheme, backward integration for fish importers and Central Bank of Nigeria Anchor borrower's programme among others. These activities are geared towards reduction of the huge fish import bill of over one billion US Dollar, food fish security, employment generation and poverty reduction. To promote aquaculture in Nigeria, the ASTRAL* EU H2020 project, is focusing on women empowerment and mainstreaming in aquaculture. More women in Nigeria are involved in fish processing and fish marketing than investment in aquaculture production. The ASTRAL project will mobilize and sensitize women in Nigeria to adopt aquaculture especially integrated multi trophic aquaculture (IMTA) as an economic activity and means of livelihood. This will increase fish production in the country, economic empowerment of the womenfolk, improve family nutrition and achievement of SDG Goal No 5 of achieving gender equality and empowering all women and girls. This paper will highlight ASTRAL's strategies for women mainstreaming in aquaculture in Nigeria.

Key Words: *ASTRAL, H2020, Women, Aquaculture, Nigeria

* ASTRAL has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 863034

Project 865034

H2020-BG-2019 All Atlantic Ocean Research Alliance Flagship

New Value Chains for Aquaculture Production

